

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 84

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 84

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 84:0 For the choir director; †on the Gittith. A Psalm of the sons of Korah.</p>	<p>Psa. 84:1 לְמִנְצַחַת עַל־הַגִּתִּית לְבְנֵי־</p>
<p>Psa. 84:1 How lovely are Your “dwelling places, O LORD of hosts!</p>	<p>קִרַּח מִזְמוֹר : 2 מֵה־יְדִירֹת</p>
<p>² My “soul longed and even yearned for the courts of the LORD;</p>	<p>מִשְׁכְּנוֹתֶיךָ יְהוָה צְבָאוֹת : 3 נִכְסְפָה</p>
<p>My heart and my flesh sing for joy to the ^aliving God.</p>	<p>וְגַם־כָּל־תָּהָה אֲנַפְשִׁי לְתַצְרוֹת יְהוָה</p>
<p>³ The bird also has found a house, And the swallow a nest for herself, where she may lay her young,</p>	<p>לִבִּי וּבִשְׂרִי יִרְנְנוּ אֵל אֱלֹהֵי : 4</p>
<p>Even Your “altars, O LORD of hosts,</p>	<p>גַּם־צִפּוֹר אֲמַצָּאָה בַּיִת וּדְרוֹר אֶקַּן</p>
<p>^bMy King and my God.</p>	<p>לָהּ אֲשֶׁר־שָׁתָה אֶפְרָתִיָּה אֶת־</p>
<p>⁴ How “blessed are those who dwell in Your house!</p>	<p>מִזְבְּחוֹתֶיךָ יְהוָה צְבָאוֹת מִלְכֵי</p>
<p>They are ^bever praising You. ¹Selah.</p>	<p>וְאֱלֹהֵי : 5 אֲשֶׁר־יֹשְׁבֵי בֵיתְךָ עוֹד</p>
<p>Psa. 84:5 How blessed is the man whose “strength is in You, In ¹whose heart are the ^bhighways to Zion!</p>	<p>יְהַלְלוּךָ סֵלָה : 6 אֲשֶׁר־אָדָם עוֹז־</p>
<p>⁶ Passing through the valley of ¹Baca they make it a ²spring;</p>	<p>לֹא בָדָד מְסֻלוֹת בְּלִבָּבָם : 7 עֲבָרֵי א</p>
<p>The “early rain also covers it with blessings.</p>	<p>בְּעֵמֶק הַבְּכָא מֵעֵינַן יִשְׁתַּוְּהוּ גַם־</p>
<p>⁷ They “go from strength to strength, ¹Every one of them ^bappears before God in Zion.</p>	<p>בְּרִכּוֹת יַעֲשֶׂה מוֹרָה : 8 יֵלְכוּ מִתַּיִל</p>
<p>Psa. 84:8 O “LORD God of hosts, hear my prayer;</p>	<p>אֵל־תַּיִל יִרְאֶה אֵל־אֱלֹהִים בְּצִיּוֹן :</p>
<p></p>	<p>יְהוָה אֱלֹהִים צְבָאוֹת שְׂמֹעַה</p>
<p></p>	<p>תִּפְלְתִי הַאֲזִינָה אֱלֹהֵי יַעֲקֹב סֵלָה :</p>
<p></p>	<p>מִגִּנְנוּ רֵאָה אֱלֹהִים וְהַבֵּט פְּנֵי</p>
<p></p>	<p>מִשִּׁיחֶךָ : 11 כִּי טוֹב־יּוֹם בְּתַצְרוֹתֶיךָ</p>
<p></p>	<p>לְמַאֲלַף בְּתַרְתֵּי הַסְּתוּפָךָ בְּבַיִת</p>
<p></p>	<p>אֱלֹהֵי מְדוּרָה בְּאַהֲלֵי־רִשְׁעָ : 12 כִּי</p>
<p></p>	<p>שָׁמַשׁ וּמִגֵּן יְהוָה אֱלֹהִים תֵּן</p>
<p></p>	<p>וְכָבוֹד יִתֵּן יְהוָה לֹא יִמְנַע־טוֹב</p>
<p></p>	<p>לְהַלְכִים בְּתַמִּים : 13 יְהוָה צְבָאוֹת</p>
<p></p>	<p>אֲשֶׁר־יִאָּדָם בְּטַח בְּךָ :</p>

<p>Give ear, O ^bGod of Jacob! Selah.</p> <p>⁹ Behold our ^ashield, O God, And look upon the face of ^bYour anointed.</p> <p>¹⁰ For ^aa day in Your courts is better than a thousand <i>outside</i>. I would rather stand at the threshold of the house of my God Than dwell in the tents of wickedness.</p> <p>¹¹ For the LORD God is ^aa sun and ^bshield; The LORD gives grace and ^cglory; ^dNo good thing does He withhold ¹from those who walk ²uprightly.</p> <p>¹² O LORD of hosts, How ^ablessed is the man who trusts in You!</p>	
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References

Psalm 84:1

^aPs 43:3; 132:5

Psalm 84:2

^aPs 42:1, 2; 63:1

^bPs 42:2

Psalm 84:3

^aPs 43:4

^bPs 5:2

Psalm 84:4

¹*Selah* may mean: *Pause, Crescendo* or *Musical interlude*

^aPs 65:4

^bPs 42:5, 11

Psalm 84:5

¹Lit *their*

^aPs 81:1

^bPs 86:11; 122:1; Jer 31:6

Psalm 84:6

¹Probably, *Weeping*; or *Balsam trees*

²Or *place of springs*

^aPs 107:35; Joel 2:23

Psalm 84:7

¹Some ancient versions read *The God of gods will be seen in Zion*

^aProv 4:18; Is 40:31; John 1:16; 2 Cor 3:18

^bEx 34:23; Deut 16:16; Ps 42:2

Psalm 84:8

^aPs 59:5; 80:4; 84:1

^bPs 81:1

Psalm 84:9

^aGen 15:1; Ps 3:3; 28:7; 59:11; 115:9-11

^b1 Sam 16:6; 2 Sam 19:21; Ps 2:2; 132:17

Psalm 84:10

^aPs 27:4

Psalm 84:11

¹Lit *with regard to*

²Lit *with integrity*

^aIs 60:19, 20; Mal 4:2; Rev 21:23

^bGen 15:1

^cPs 85:9

^dPs 34:9, 10

Psalm 84:12

^aPs 2:12; 40:4

Targum

Psa. 84:1 For praise, on the lyre that comes from Gath; composed by the sons of Korah; a psalm. ² How beloved are your tents, O LORD Sabaoth! ³ My soul craved and even yearned for the court of the LORD; my heart and flesh meditate on the enduring God. ⁴ Even the dove has found a house, and the turtledove a nest that is suitable for her hatchlings – to be sacrificed on your altars, O LORD Sabaoth, my king and my God. ⁵ Happy are the righteous who dwell in your sanctuary; again they will praise you forever. ⁶ Happy the man who has his strength in your word; trust is in their hearts. ⁷ The wicked who cross over the valleys of Gehenna, weeping – he will make their weeping like a fountain; also those who return to the teaching of his Torah he will cover with blessings. ⁸ The righteous go from the sanctuary to the academies; their toil in the Torah will be manifest before the LORD, whose presence abides in Zion. ⁹ David said, “O LORD, God Sabaoth, receive my prayer; hear, O God of Jacob, forever.” ¹⁰ See, O God, the merits of our fathers, and behold, the face of your anointed. ¹¹ For it is better to dwell one day in the courtyard of your sanctuary than a thousand in exile; I have chosen to adhere to the sanctuary of God rather than to live in the tents of wickedness. ¹² For the LORD God is like a high wall and a strong shield; the LORD will give grace and glory; he will not hide goodness from those who walk in perfection. ¹³ O LORD Sabaoth, it is well for the son of man who trusts in your word.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This is the first Psalm that was written by the sons of Korach.

“Korach incites a mutiny challenging Moses’ leadership and the granting of the *kehunah* (priesthood) to Aaron. He is accompanied by Moses’ inveterate foes, Dathan and Abiram. Joining them are 250 distinguished members of the community, who offer the sacrosanct *ketoret* (incense) to prove their worthiness for the priesthood. The earth opens up and swallows the mutineers, and a fire consumes the *ketoret*-offerers.”¹

The sage Radak commented that the Psalm was inspired by King David’s experiences when he fled from Saul and entered Philistia. David yearned to return to Israel to see the Ark of the Covenant. David expressed the innermost ongoing of all the lonely exiles in future generations.

Superscript

To the Sefirah Netzach, who grants victory upon the wine pressings. By the sons of Korach, a Psalm.

Verse two

According to the Zohar, 4/5 of the soul is spiritual. The spiritual soul yearns to be close to the LORD. When David was in exile, his soul yearned to be where the LORD was. In his days, the general belief was that the LORD only resided in the land of Israel.

¹ “Korach - Parshah - Weekly Torah Portion - Chabad,” accessed January 17, 2023, https://www.chabad.org/parshah/default_cdo/aid/45591/jewish/Korach.htm.

My soul yearns; indeed, it pines for the courts of the LORD; my heart and my body sing with joy toward the living God.

Verse four

Forward forever stride those that dwell in Your House; continually they proclaim Your praise. Meditate on this verse.

Verse six

The valley of weeping filled with tears is a metaphor for David's sorrow because he believed he was disconnected from the LORD. When the people of Judah were exiled into the land of Babylon, they felt disconnected from the LORD and longed to return to their homeland.

Wandering through the valley of weeping, they make it into a spring; indeed, into blessings with which a rain envelops.

Verse eight

The phrase "God of Jacob" raises the speculation that the Psalmist knew Israel followed the LORD's Laws of the Torah. However, like Jacob, they got into the gray areas and perhaps crossed the line in a few ways. Jacob was a trickster in fooling his brother Esau into giving him the birthright and the blessing of their father, Isaac. The Psalmist is reminding Israel that they have been tricksters before the LORD.

O God, God of Hosts, hear my prayer; incline your ear, O God of Jacob.
Meditate on this verse.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

